

Valorization of Waste Plastic Bottles and Diapers in the Production of Sustainable Pavement Blocks

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Abstract- Plastic and diaper waste are major pollution problems worldwide. Approximately 72% of global plastic and diaper wastes end up in landfills, exacerbating environmental degradation, highlighting the urgent need for valorization strategies. This study investigated the potential use of Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) plastics, diaper wastes and sand for the production of pavement blocks, with the goal of developing an environmentally sustainable method for repurposing these waste materials into valuable construction products. Four formulations of the paving blocks were produced and their mechanical and physical properties evaluated through various testing methods. For the four formulations, the plastic (binder) content was maintained at a constant 45% while the diaper (aggregate) content was being varied across formulations, replacing sand at percentages of 0%, 2.5%, 5% and 10% respectively. The results showed that the compressive strength of the blocks remained relatively constant across the first three formulations, with values of 10.23 MPa, 10.25 MPa, and 10.25 MPa, respectively, but dropped significantly in the fourth formulation (5.57 MPa). This indicated that a 10% replacement of sand by diapers in the fourth formulation is not advisable, as their compressive strength falls below the minimum of 8.5 MPa recommended by the SNI 03-0691-1996 standard. Moreover, the results also indicated that both flexural strength and abrasion resistance of the blocks declined as the diaper concentration increased, suggesting an optimal threshold concentration for incorporating waste diapers into the waste blocks. Also, the water absorption rate of the paving blocks increased with increasing diaper concentration with values of 0.34%, 0.34%, 0.92%, and 2.18%, respectively. However, all values were within the <20% limit for high quality blocks (ISS 1077-1970 Standard) suggesting that the blocks can withstand extreme environmental conditions, such as floods. The research demonstrates the potential to co-valorize waste plastics, diapers, and sand for the production of sustainable pavement blocks.

Index Terms-Plastic waste, diaper waste, pavement blocks, mechanical properties, environmental sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION

As global waste generation continues to rise, identifying sustainable waste management solutions has become an urgent environmental imperative. As of 2023, the annual production of municipal solid waste (MSW) surpasses 2.1 billion tons, with projections suggesting a 70% increase, potentially reaching 3.8 billion metric tons by 2050 [1]. Considering the current global population of 8.1 billion, with a projected rise to nearly 10 billion by 2050 [2], it is evident that this surge will dramatically impact global waste production due to population increase, demanding a sustained exploration of waste valorization channels.

Moreover, within the African context, in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA), the MSW generation stood at 174 million tons as of 2018 and is projected to rise to 269 and 516 million tons by the years 2030 and 2050 respectively [3], with an estimated population rise from 1.03 billion to 2 billion by the year 2050 [4]. Narrowing to the Cameroonian scenario, as of 2022, with a population of about 27.9 million, the country generated over 5.5 million tons of waste [5]. This has been forecasted to rise from 5.8 to 11.8 million tons by year 2030 and 2050 respectively, with corresponding population increase from 32 million to 48 million people respectively too [3].

This increasing volume of waste engenders significant environmental concerns and necessitates the pursuit of

innovative waste valorization methods. Some of these concerns include aesthetic degradation, water contamination, drainage blockages, fire hazards and vector breeding ground within urban areas. Notably, waste diapers and plastic bottles represent sizable contributors to the burgeoning waste streams. Globally, waste baby diapers contribute between 0.2% and 22.2% of municipal solid waste (MSW) and are predominantly consigned to landfills or incineration ([6], [7]). In parallel, global plastic production is currently about 400 metric tons annually while global plastic waste production is estimated at 353 metric tons annually [8]. Unfortunately, a mere 9% of the plastic waste generated has been recycled, while 19% is incinerated, leaving a substantial 72% to be disposed of in landfills or unrestrained in the environment [9].

Looking at previous works, Ref. [10] and [11] used sand and melted plastics to produce pavement blocks that were good enough to use in paving public road and parking lots based on their compressive strength and water absorption results. However, this present seeks not only to repurpose plastic waste alone, but other non-plastic waste such as is present in baby diapers. This is also in line with the recommendations of Ref. [12] who after a recent study realized that the association of plastic and non-plastics in some materials was a barrier to their valorization, because separation, which is often time-consuming and costly, is required. And so, to overcome this barrier, they recommended the mixing of plastic waste with different waste materials in the production of construction materials to provide the co-benefit of reducing other types of waste, and also the testing of different combinations of raw materials, including non-plastic waste and plastic waste, as critical to identifying the formula that produces construction materials with desirable properties. Also, Ref. [13] recently used waste diapers alongside gravel, sand, cement and water to produce pavement blocks that could be used to pave gardens and floors. Despite the success of this novel approach, there is still significant dependence on finite, natural materials to produce the blocks, which is what this present study seeks to significantly minimize.

The construction sector, renowned for its substantial resource consumption, consuming up to 40% of the world's raw resources, presents an opportunity to redirect waste materials from landfills and advocate for circular economy principles [14].

Cement, gravel and sand are traditional components of pavement blocks, offering strength, durability and stability. Cement, a hydraulic binder, provides cohesion and compressive strength, while sand and gravel serve as aggregates, enhancing the blocks overall stability and drainage [15]. However, the increasing demand for pavement materials, coupled with environmental concerns and depletion of natural resources, necessitates the exploration of alternative material. In this context, the valorization of waste diapers and

plastic bottles in road pavement production presents a significant potential for resource recovery and waste mitigation. Diapers composed of cellulose-based materials, superabsorbent polymers, and plastic layers, offer a unique recycling opportunity [16]. Plastic bottles, which can be melted and used as binders in road construction materials, provide another innovative solution. Utilizing these waste materials can significantly reduce reliance on natural resources such as sand, water, gravel and those used to produce cement. This strategy not only conserves natural resources but also helps mitigate the environmental impacts associated with traditional road construction methods ([17], [18]).

The primary objective of this study was therefore to explore the feasibility of utilizing shredded waste diapers (SWD) and plastic bottles in the fabrication of pavement bricks through a process involving melting and mixing with sand. Subsequently, the mechanical and physical properties of these bricks were rigorously assessed. This aimed to determine the suitability and potential advantages of the novel bricks for sustainable road construction practices.

1. Location and Description of the Study Area

The study was conducted in Bamenda III municipality found in the Mezam Division of the Northwest Region of Cameroon (Figure 1). More specifically, the experiments were conducted at GEOSTRUCT, a civil engineering laboratory located in Mile 4, Bamenda III, and at the Civil Engineering Laboratory of Government Technical High School, Mile 3 Bamenda III. Bamenda III is located between Longitudes 10°10'0" and 10°14'0" East of the Greenwich Meridian and between Latitudes 5°56'0" and 6°0'0" North of the Equator [19].

Bamenda III sub division is the gateway to and from the Divisions of Boyo, Ngokentunja, Bui and Donga Mantung. It is an important transit for passengers and goods to and from the North West Region. It is bounded by Tubah Sub Division to the West, Bamenda I Sub-Division to North, and Bamenda II Sub Division to the East and Bafut to the South.

It has a total area of 22.9 km² and a population estimated at 150,000 inhabitants with a 6% increase per annum [20]. The two autonomous villages of Nkwen and Ndzah make up the Bamenda III Sub-Division. There are 46 quarters in Nkwen and 9 in Ndzah village.

The urban space population is about 95,000 inhabitants. This population is largely cosmopolitan, made up of indigenous Nkwen and Ndzah people together with migrants from all over the North West, West and other Regions of Cameroon including Nigerians, Chadians, and Equatorial Guineans [21].

Fig 1: Map showing Mezam Division and the North West region within Cameroon (A), Bamenda III within Mezam Division (B) and Bamenda III (C).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Collection and Preparation of Materials

The materials used for this study primarily included Polyethylene Terapthalate (PET) plastic bottles, diapers, and river bed sand. PET bottles were chosen as the main binder due to their abundance in waste streams in Bamenda III. River bed sand, selected for its availability, served as the main aggregate. Waste diapers were incorporated as a partial replacement of the aggregate to produce the paving blocks.

The plastics were retrieved from homes, dustbins, dumpsites, and gutters within the Bamenda III subdivision. Approximately 15Kg of plastics were used in the research work. As this study centered on a specific type of plastic, PET, the bottle lids and labels were carefully removed and separated from the material utilized in the experiment. This process ensured that the plastic composition remained solely PET for accurate analysis. Plastics were shredded with a scissors to reduce their surface area and hasten their melting process. Shredding also helps increase the volume of plastics that can be melted at a particular time.

From random sampling, the diaper brand used in this study was Softcare baby diapers. Diapers sourced from the market were simulated to resemble used diapers stained with urine, following the methodology outlined by [18]. Consistent with their approach, new diapers were shredded and combined with Sodium Chloride solution to emulate the characteristics of diapers stained with urine. Sodium chloride was employed in accordance with the testing methodologies outlined by both

the European Disposable and Nonwovens Association (EDANA) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). These established methods utilize saline as the test medium to assess parameters such as free swell capacity, fluid retention, and fluid absorption under pressure in diaper components intended for use as urine absorbing aids in cases of incontinence ([22],[23],[24],[25],[26][27]). The concentration of salt (NaCl) was three weight percent of ambient dry diapers. simulated used diapers, in place of actual used diapers, were utilized in this study because the manual handling of waste diapers is greatly discouraged given that infants serve as particularly effective carriers of enteric pathogens, leading to an increase in microbial pathogens within solid waste in diapers [28]. A total of about 60 diapers (approximately 1.44Kg) were used in the entire research. River sand was sourced from the Lab where the study was carried out.

2. Experimental Design

The experimental design comprised four formulations, each distinguished by the varying quantity of waste diapers integrated into the mixture of PET, waste diapers and sand. The control experiment, devoid of any waste diapers, served as the baseline for comparison. All formulations were replicated three times giving a total of 12 samples so that the average for each of the four formulations could be obtained (Table 1). The percentage composition of the plastic binder was kept constant at 45%. This was because varying it was going to affect the strength of the blocks making it difficult to establish the unique effects of the different diapers proportions on the strength of the blocks.

Table 1: Formulation of the Pavement Blocks

Formulations (F)	Sample I.D	Materials weight (%)		
		PET	Diaper	Sand
Formulation 1 (Control Mix)	F1S1	45	0	55
	F1S2			
	F1S3			
Formulation 2	F2S1	45	2.5	52.5
	F2S2			
	F2S3			
Formulation 3	F3S1	45	5	55
	F3S2			
	F3S3			
Formulation 4	F4S1	45	10	45
	F4S2			
	F3S4			

F=Formulation, S=Sample

The concentration of the aggregates (sand and diapers) was being varied, with diapers replacing sand in different percentages. This was to find the diaper proportion which gives the best minimum acceptable results according to

international standards. Diaper replacement of 2.5%, and 5% and 10% were chosen because a recent study by Ref. [13] suggested that the maximum replacement of sand with diapers is 10%, if a comprehensive strength of 10MPa will be achieved. Therefore, this research worked around that range.

3. Batching and Heating

Sand was weighed according to the respective percentages using an analogue scale, while diapers and plastics were weighed using an electronic scale for better accuracy. To calculate their respective weight compositions per formulation, a total mixture weight was randomly determined (9 kg) and their respective percentage compositions calculated using Equation (1):

$$\text{Material composition} = \frac{\text{Weight}}{\text{Total weight}} \quad (1)$$

The waste materials to be used, upon shredding, were then melted by heating in a metal drum using wood fuel. The drum was first heated to remove moisture before introducing the materials. Also, the sand was heated to remove moisture and to facilitate the bonding process by avoiding a sudden drop in the mixtures temperature upon introduction. Shredded diapers were mixed with the melted plastics and when the plastics had completely melted, sand was added gradually and stirring was done by means of a stirring rod until the material was ready for casting. If the mixing is not done properly, the resulting product will not have a homogeneous texture and this will have a negative effect on the block's properties.

4. Molding of Blocks

Once the mixture had an appropriate texture, they were carefully casted into lubricated molds. The molds for testing samples were according to international standards, 7x7x7 cm and 16x4x4 cm for compressive and flexural strength respectively. The molds were lubricated to ease demolding. Because the mixture was extremely hot with temperatures exceeding 270°C (melting point of PET), casting was done by means of a trowel to avoid contact with the hand. Casting must be done quickly because the mixture hardens rapidly and if there is delay, the block will have different textures and this will eventually play out negatively on the blocks strength. Before allowing for solidification inside the molds, the mixture was compressed by a hand compressor, in order to eliminate airspaces within the sample. The blocks were then left for cooling and drying in air before removal from the molds.

5. Testing of Mechanical Properties of the Paving Blocks

Compressive Strength Test: This was determined after 24 hours of curing following the BS 5628: Part 1: 1992 procedures [29], using the universal testing machine (UTM machine), LM-02 Type Digital Dynamometry Appa, Zhejiang Tugong. After properly positioning the block in the machine, the load was applied on the block without any

shock. The load was increased at a rate of 140 kg/cm² min continuously till the samples resistance to increasing load breaks down and it could not withstand any greater load further. Recording of the maximum load applied to the block samples was noted. 12 samples (Figure 2) from the 4 different formulations (3 samples per formulation) were tested and the average compressive strength of each formulation determined. The compressive strength of plastic pavement bricks was calculated using Equation (2):

$$\text{Compressive strength} = \frac{\text{Force (N)}}{\text{Cross Sectional Area (mm}^2\text{)}} \quad (2)$$

Fig 2: Blocks samples used for compressive strength.

Flexural Strength Test: Following the ASTM C 293-15 procedure [30], this test involved applying a transverse force perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the pavers. A central line was marked on top of each paver, perpendicular to its length, to guide the testing process. This was to ensure that the force is applied equally on the block. The pavers were placed on two support rods spanning 150mm and subjected to a central line load until failure using the universal testing machine

In this study, the test was conducted on 16x4x4cm blocks as recommended by the ASTM C293-15 Standard (Figure 3). The recorded flexural strength values represent the average of 3 samples for each of the four formulations of paver, allowing for comprehensive and reliable assessments of their performance under stress. The modulus of rupture was calculated using equation (3):

$$R = \frac{PL}{bd^2} \quad (3)$$

where: R= modulus of rupture, psi, or MPa; P= maximum applied load indicated by the testing machine, N; L= span length, in mm; b= average width of specimen, mm.

Figure 3: Block samples for flexural strength.

6. Testing the Physical Properties of the Blocks

Water Absorption Test: In this test, according to the ISS 1077-1970 protocol [31], the bricks were weighed in total dry conditions after molding. This weight was recorded as W1. The blocks were then dipped completely in fresh water for up to 24hrs in a container, after which they were taken out of the water, wiped with a cloth and their second weights (W2) recorded. This was to observe if there are significant changes in their water absorption rate over time.

The test was conducted on a total of 12 samples of the 4 formulations, 3 samples per formulation. The averages of the water absorption rate were then taken as representative of that particular formulation. The water absorption rate of each plastic pavement brick was then calculated using equation (4).

$$= \frac{\text{Weight of wet brick (W}_2\text{)} - \text{Weight of dry brick (W}_1\text{)}}{\text{Weight of dry brick (W}_1\text{)}} * 100 \quad (4)$$

Abrasion Resistance (ASTM C 902-15): Going by the ASTM C 902-15 standards [32], abrasive resistance is a measure of the resistance of paving brick to the wearing action due to traffic. This was calculated using equation (5):

$$\text{Abrasive index} = \frac{\text{Water absorption}}{\text{compressive strength (psi)}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

(1Mpa = 145.038 psi).

III. RESULT AND INTERPRETATION

1. Mechanical Properties of the Pavement Blocks

Compressive Strength of the Pavement Blocks: The average compressive strength of Formulation 1 (control) bricks was 10.23 MPa. The strength for Formulation 2 and 3 were the same, 10.25 MPa, slightly higher than that of Formulation 1 and remained constant even with a diaper replacement of 2.5% up to 5% of sand. However, at the 10% diaper replacement (Formulation 4), there was a very

significant drop in the compressive strength of the blocks to 5.57 MPa. Based on the SNI 03-0691-1996 standard, the blocks of the first 3 Formulations can be classified as quality D blocks (blocks with a compressive strength of between 8.5 and 12 MPa) and can be used in gardens. The blocks of Formulation 4 fall below acceptable standards (Figure 4).

Fig 4: Compressive strength of the different formulations

Flexural Strength of the Pavement Blocks: The flexural strengths of the blocks decreased with increasing diaper concentration. The paving blocks with compressive strengths of 10.23 MPa, 10.25 MPa, 10.25 MPa and 5.58 MPa, had corresponding flexural strengths of 3.96 MPa, 3.88 MPa, 3 MPa and 1.53 MPa respectively (Figure 5).

Fig 5: Flexural strength of the different formulations

2. Physical Properties of the Paving Blocks

Water Absorption Rate of the Pavement Blocks: In this study, it was observed that the amount of waste diapers in the pavement brick affected their water absorption rates. As the amount of waste diapers in the plastic pavement brick increased, the water absorption rate also increased. The lowest water absorption (0.34%) was recorded for Formulation 1 pavement bricks with 45% of plastics and 55% of sand and no diapers. In contrast, the highest water absorption of 2.18% was recorded with Formulation 4 pavement bricks when 10% of diaper, 45% sand and 45% plastic was used (Figure 6).

The water absorption rates of all plastic pavement blocks were within the range of those of the high-quality ones, that is, less than 20%, based on the ISS 1077-1970 standard. They can therefore be classified as quality 1 pavements used for public roads.

Fig 6: Water absorption rate of the different formulations

Abrasive Index of the Paving Blocks: The abrasive resistance of the paving blocks decreased with an increase in diaper replacement of sand, from 0.02 at the 2.5% replacement up to 0.27 at the 10% replacement level (Figure 7). Based on the ASTM C 902-15 standard, the blocks of Formulation 1 to 3, with a maximum of 5% diaper replacement, can be classified as Type I pavements blocks because their abrasive index is less than 0.11, meaning they can theoretically be used in public roads as they offer a high resistance to abrasion. Also, the blocks of Formulation 4, with 10% diaper replacement of sand, can be classified as Type II paving blocks because their abrasive index (0.27) falls within the prescribed range, meaning that theoretically, they can be used for vehicle parking. The results of the Calculated Abrasive index of the paving blocks are presented in Figure 7.

Fig 7: Abrasion resistance of the paving block

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Mechanical Properties of the Blocks

Compressive Strength: From formulation 1 to 2, there is a slight increase in compressive strength. This slight increase could be because the diaper particles act as fillers, effectively occupying the void spaces between the sand particles, thereby reducing porosity and increasing the overall density of the composite material. This densification and improved interlocking mechanism contribute to the increased compressive strength observed in the plastic-sand cubes [32].

However, the compressive strengths reported in this study are relatively lower than those reported in other studies (eg. [33], [11]). This could have been because of the following reasons:

Generally, PET gives low compressive strength and this could be because of its low density as Ref. [34] suggested. PET plastic has limited resistance to low temperatures. At low temperatures, PET plastic can become brittle and susceptible to cracking or breaking. This is based on Ref. [35] explanation that PET plastic has the disadvantage of not being impact resistant so it is easily damaged, more difficult to shape and easily changes shape when in contact with hot temperatures. Ref. [36] also observed that PET plastic hardened more quickly, and this caused the printing process not to have maximum time, causing the paving blocks to crack easily. Therefore, this is possibly one of the reasons why the pavement blocks had low compressive strengths. Ref. [37] did a comparative study of Sand-PET and Sand-HDPE paving blocks. Their results indicated that an increase in PET reduced the compressive strength of the paving blocks, while an increase in HDPE content increased the compressive strengths of the blocks. They therefore concluded that the use of the

sand-PET mix when PET acts as the only binding material should be avoided. Also, the relatively low compressive strengths reported in this present study may have been because a good PET:sand ratio was not used. Ref. [38] manufactured bricks by incorporating melted PET bottles with manufactured sand. They reported that the compressive strength increased along with plastics content up to a certain limit and subsequently, it decreased. This shows that there is an optimum PET to sand ratio that exist. Ref. [39] found that it was 1:2 while Ref. [32] reported the optimum ratio to be 1:4. Contrary to this, the ratio used in this study was nearly a 1:1. Lastly, especially for the last formulation with a low and unacceptable compressive strength of 5.57 MPa, the possible reason for this is because of the high level (10%) replacement of sand by diapers. This is in alignment with the findings of Ref. [13] who reported that the maximum replacement rate of waste diapers in concrete is 9%, to achieve strength of 10 MPa. They found that more than 9% substitution of fine aggregates with disposable diapers is not allowed for paving blocks due to the strength being below the specifications, thus indicating that the ideal level of replacement with respect to this current study lies between 5% and 9%.

Flexural Strength: Generally, flexural strength of concrete is usually between 10 to 20% of the compressive strength [40]. For formulation 1 to 4, the flexural strength corresponded to 38%, 37%, 29% and 27.5% respectively of their compressive strengths. This unusually high flexural strength results show that the use of plastics as binders enhanced the flexural strength of the blocks. This is similar with the findings of Ref. [33] who reported a flexural strength of 6.04 MPa for plastic pavement blocks, representing 24.5% of the blocks compressive strength. Nonetheless, as the diaper content of the blocks increased, the flexural strength reduced accordingly.

3. Physical Properties of the Pavement Blocks

Water Absorption: The results of the first two formulations reported in this study are very similar to those of Ref. [33] and [38] who all reported a decrease in water absorption as PET content increased. Ref. [33] specifically recorded a water absorption rate of 0.369% for their plastic pavers, similar to those of formulation 1 and 2 of this study (0.34%). The reason for the low water absorption of formulation 1 pavers is due to the hydrophobicity of the plastics and the absence of diaper in their mixtures. As for formulation 2, the low water absorption is because the diaper content was relatively low (2.5%) compared to those of formulations 3 and 4. This shows that at the 2.5% level of replacement, the water absorption rate of the blocks isn't affected. For formulation 3 and 4, a significant increase was noticed in the water absorption rate, 0.92% and 2.18% respectively, and this increase was obviously due to the fact that their disposable diapers concentration was much higher, 5% and 10% respectively. Superabsorbent polymers (SAPs) have a high absorption capacity, making them suitable

for holding significant amounts of liquid within the diaper. So, the SAPs exhibit their innate absorbent properties, affecting the water absorption characteristics of the bricks. These results are consistent with those of Ref. [11] who reported an average water absorption rate of 2.25% for plastic:pit sand pavers. The excellent water absorption property of the sand-waste plastic paving blocks can be attributed to the hydrophobic nature of the plastic [10]. In addition, the bond between the sand and melted plastic helped in reducing air voids in the aggregate, thereby leading to decreased permeability of the mixture [41]. Consequently, these blocks can therefore be used in extreme environmental conditions such as high rainfalls without being damaged easily.

Abrasion Resistance: As diaper content increased, a drop in abrasion resistance was noticed. This is possibly because increased diaper content of the blocks caused the blocks to become softer. However, the overall theoretical abrasion resistance of the blocks was very good. The very low abrasion resistance value recorded by the plastic pavers indicates that plastic pavers have high ability to withstand wearing action than traditional cement pavers which is a result of the good adherence of the plastic with the sand aggregates. The results reported in this study are similar to those of Ref. [33] who reported abrasive indexes of 0.014 for plastic pavement blocks. However, the theoretically derived abrasive index of the blocks is an inferior property as compared to the mechanically derived compressive strength of the blocks, and so, compressive strength should be the first and most important criteria to consider before determining the use of the blocks.

V. CONCLUSION

This project investigated the feasibility of utilizing sand and waste materials, specifically waste plastics, and diapers, as components in the production of pavement blocks. The results show that durable pavement blocks can be produced from these waste materials. The blocks can be used for low traffic areas such as homes and gardens. The successful incorporation of these waste materials into pavement blocks demonstrates a potential pathway for diverting them from landfills and promoting a circular economy. Also, using these materials reduces reliance on natural materials that have traditionally been used for the production of conventional pavement blocks, mitigating the environmental footprint associated with their extraction and processing.

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